

**EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND CLINICAL TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS
AMONG THE FACULTY OF MEDICAL-RELATED PROGRAMS IN CEBU
DOCTORS' UNIVERSITY: PROPOSALS IN THE INTEGRATION OF
THE INSTITUTIONAL FACULTY DEVELOPMENT PLAN**

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Emotional Intelligence and Clinical Teaching Effectiveness among the Faculty of Medical-Related Programs in Cebu Doctors' University: Proposals in the Integration of the Institutional Faculty Development Plan

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness of the faculty of medical-related programs in Cebu Doctors' University and the relationship between them in order to utilize the findings for the proposals in the integration of the institutional faculty development plan. The respondents included were 186 employed full-time or part-time medical-related faculty members of the different programs. A descriptive–correlational research design was utilized. The two (2) research instruments used was Emotional Intelligence Scale and Modified Clinical Teacher Effectiveness Inventory. An increase emotional intelligence mean score indicates that the respondent has a greater sense of self-awareness regarding emotions toward others and themselves, as well as social skills in managing and utilizing emotions to develop positive attitudes that improve problem-solving and clinical decision-making. Whereas, increase clinical teaching effectiveness mean score indicates that the respondents has high teaching behavior in transmitting theoretical and clinical knowledge used in the practice and the attitudes toward the profession, greater occurrence in the type and amount of feedback regarding his/her clinical performance. The relationship between emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness showed no relationship on all the aspects. A proposal entitled “Enhancing Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Effectiveness Among Medical-Related Faculty” was integrated to the institutional faculty development plan as to improve the faculty with low emotional intelligence and moderate clinical teaching effectiveness in regards with personal, emotional and social aspects in translating to know thyself and others' need. Based on the findings, this study served as the basis for the university's institutional development plan, which appropriately addressed the importance of emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness among faculty by financing the plan to be implemented through seminars/workshops to promote faculty well-being – teaching behavior and interpersonal relations with others..

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, clinical teaching effectiveness, faculty*

Introduction

In the late 20th century, emphasis on the intelligence quotient of faculty was of utmost importance in the measurement of success in the profession. After a punctilious observation of the factors leading to professional success, psychologists realized that cognitive intelligence alone is not a guarantee for success in teaching. Many factors have been identified, including emotional intelligence.

Emotional intelligence has been defined as “the intelligent use of emotions: one intentionally makes one’s own emotion work for one by using them to help guide one’s behaviour and thinking in ways that enhance one’s result” (Weisenger, 1998). It is otherwise known as emotional quotient or emotional competency which helps in prioritizing thinking, behaviour and lifestyle as an indicator of clinical teaching effectiveness. Individuals who have developed high level of emotional intelligence are able to recognize and regulate their own and others emotions (Jaeger, 2003). These abilities are important prerequisites for establishing wholesome relationships with other people.

For faculty, emotional intelligence is important toward success in dealing with students. Emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness are vital qualities that creates a conducive teaching-learning atmosphere. Clinical teaching effectiveness in higher education is a complex interplay of the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and personal characteristics of faculty, but clinical teaching encompasses unique competencies that may differ from those needed in a classroom setting (Fluit, Bolhuis, Grol, Laan, & Wensing, 2010; Tigelaar, Dolmans, Wolfhagen, & Van Der Vleuten, 2004). CDU faculty or clinical instructors help students synthesize theoretical and experiential knowledge, and clinical teaching is one of the most effective pedagogies in education yet effectiveness of clinical faculty can either facilitate or hinder the process. Hanson and Stenvig (2008) found that the competence of clinical faculty to bridge the gap between the three (3) domains of learning was identified by students as part of a successful clinical experience. However, unlike ordinary classroom instruction, clinical teaching is secondary to the goals of the health care facility, as patient care must take precedence over the students’ learning needs (Allison-Jones & Hirt, 2004). This characteristic leaves clinical faculty with competing goals as they juggle students’ learning needs with the safety of patients and the goals of the health care facility. Perhaps due to the unpredictability of the environment and the inability to focus solely on students’ learning needs, clinical teaching often focuses on the attainment of psychomotor skills (Benner et al., 2010). This is unfortunate because opportunities for affective learning that could contribute to the development of emotional intelligence may be lost where it is evident in the clinical teaching of Cebu Doctors' University.

CDU clinical instructors are not only responsible for imparting the subject matter among their students, but should also be a mentor,

friend, and colleague to the students. One should build confidence among the students by discussing with them their academic progress, peer to peer relationships, and learning needs. These qualities are expected of the clinical faculty of Cebu Doctors' University since it is a means to improve the student learning experience and the connectedness between faculty and students where importance of clear clinical procedures demonstration and techniques, by encouraging active participation during the discussion and promotes student independence in the clinical and community settings. In the performance of these functions, the faculty may experience drawbacks that are caused by many factors related to the teaching-learning situation. In some cases, teachers may feel emotionally affected by their students' academic inadequacies which teachers associate with their own teaching efficiency and effectiveness by demonstrating a hostile behavior and feedback towards colleague, student and peers. They tend to become emotional although knowing that emotions need to be understood, taught, trained and controlled by the mind (Roja, Sasikumar & Fathima, 2013).

In view of this, the researcher has been motivated to determine the emotional intelligence and the teaching effectiveness of clinical instructors and to evaluate the relationship between these variables. Knowing the importance of emotional intelligence as a means to establish rapport with co-teachers and students, the researcher conducted this study as to propose a plan by sustaining the high emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness of the majority of the faculty and to develop those faculty who have low emotional intelligence and moderate clinical teaching effectiveness as to enhance their personal, emotional and social aspects in translating to know thyself and others' need. It aimed to integrate this proposal into the human behavior component of the faculty development plan to attain competent, exemplary performance of the entire medical-related faculty of Cebu Doctors' University.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness of the faculty of medical-related programs in Cebu Doctors' University and the relationship between them in the Academic Year 2017-2018 in order to utilize the findings to formulate proposals for integration in the institutional faculty development plan. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the emotional intelligence mean score among the faculty of medical-related programs in terms of:
 - 1.1. perception of emotions;
 - 1.2. managing emotions in the self;
 - 1.3. social skills on managing others' emotions; and
 - 1.4. utilizing emotions?
2. What is the clinical teaching effectiveness mean score among the faculty of medical-related programs in terms of:
 - 2.1. teaching ability;
 - 2.2. teaching competence;
 - 2.3. evaluation;
 - 2.4. interpersonal relations; and
 - 2.5. personality?
3. Is there a relationship between the mean score of emotional intelligence and the clinical teaching effectiveness among medical-related faculty in CDU?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what proposals may be presented for integration in the Institutional Faculty Development Plan?

Literature Review

Emotional Intelligence and Clinical Teaching Effectiveness

Theory of Jaeger (2003) who stated that emotional intelligence helps an individual to recognize and regulate their emotions and those of others. Emotion is defined as a psychological state that arises spontaneously rather than through conscious effort and is sometimes accompanied by psychological changes associated with feelings. It is a response in the low level of subcortical regions of the brain, the amygdala and the ventromedial prefrontal cortices, which creates biochemical reactions in the body altering one's physical state. Originally, it helps the species survive by producing quick reactions to threat, reward, and everything in between in their environments. Emotional reactions are coded in the genes and slightly vary among individual depending on the circumstances (James, 1884).

The philosophical context of clinical teaching refers to the teacher's understanding of his/her role, approaches to clinical teaching, selection of teaching and learning activities, use of evaluation process, and relationships with learners and others in the clinical environment. Clinical instruction serve as a guide to action, and profoundly affect clinical teacher practice, how students learn, and how learning outcomes are evaluated. Reflecting on the philosophical basis for one's clinical teaching may evoke anxiety about exposing oneself and one's practice to scrutiny, but this self-reflection is a meaningful basis for continued professional development as an educator (Gaberson & Oermann, 2010). This is where clinical teaching effectiveness (CTE) is derived from as to measure outcome of a teaching-learning process that enables students to apply theoretical knowledge, psychomotor skills, and affective attitudes to ever-changing patient situations, and requires a different set of skills than classroom instruction (AACN, 2008; Knox & Mogan, 1985; Ondrejka, 2013).

Methodology

Participants

The participants included in this study were one hundred eighty six (186) full-time or part-time medical-related faculty members of the different curricular programs offered in Cebu Doctors' University. This faculty members were categorized as clinical instructors since they were directly involved in teaching students upon handling patients in the clinical practice. The following colleges involved in this study were the College of Nursing, College of Allied Medical Sciences, College of Rehabilitative Sciences, College of Dentistry, College of Optometry and College of Medicine. Respondents excluded in the study was from the Graduate School, College of Pharmacy and College of Arts and Sciences since the faculty of these colleges are not involved in patient interaction.

Instruments

For a qualitative study, the researcher utilized two (2) research instruments – Emotional Intelligence Scale and Modified Clinical Teacher Effectiveness Inventory for data collection. The Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS) is a 33-item self-report inventory focusing on typical emotional intelligence. In some literature, it is otherwise known as assessing emotions scale, the self-report emotional intelligence test and Schutte Emotional Intelligence Scale. It assess the characteristic, or trait, emotional intelligence in four factors: (1) perception of emotions, (2) managing emotions in the self, (3) social skills or managing others' emotions, and (4) utilizing emotions by Ciarrochi et al., (2001). The respondents rated themselves on the items using a five-point scale as "1" (strongly disagree), the "2" (somewhat disagree), "3" (neither agree nor disagree), "4" (somewhat agree) and "5" (strongly agree) that the descriptions fitted them. Every response is equivalent to points, the total scores are calculated by reverse coding items 5, 28 and 33, and then summing all items. Scores can range from 33 to 165, with higher scores indicating more characteristic emotional intelligence. In some cases, the means reported in the research article or chapter were the average of all scale items rather than the sum of scale items. The mean scores ranging from 1.0-3.42 can be categorized as low emotional intelligence and a score ranging from 3.43-5.0 can be categorized as high emotional intelligence. This can be interpreted on how the respondents understand the non-verbal messages of other people and vice versa, the sense of controlling his/her emotion over things and being optimistic in most of the time. A pilot testing has been conducted among 45 respondents with the same norm group on the actual respondents since there were items need to be modified as to tailor fit the tool used. Based on the result of the pilot testing conducted in the four factors, the reliability statistics for perception of emotions (items 1-10) revealed 0.713. The managing emotions in the self (items 11-19) and social skills on managing others' emotions (items 20-27) showed a Cronbach's alpha of 0.731 and 0.737 respectively. Lastly, utilizing emotions (items 28-33) has a reliability statistics of 0.819 which all four factors were accepted.

Modified Clinical Teacher Effectiveness Inventory (MCTEI) is a 48-item self-report modified survey instrument that measures the clinical teaching effectiveness of the clinical instructors in the different medical programs that derived from the "Knox and Mogan Nursing Clinical Teacher Effectiveness Inventory" (NCTEI-1985). Certain modification of the questionnaire to incorporate items to be applicable in all medical-related faculty. The items are divided into five teaching behavior competences that provides a total score: (1) teaching ability, (2) teaching competence, (3) evaluation, (4) interpersonal relations, and (5) personality by Mogan & Knox (1983). The respondents were asked to rate each item on a 7 point Likert-type scale as "1" = very unimportant, "2" = unimportant, "3" = minimally important, "4" = somewhat important, "5" = moderately important, "6" = important and "7" = very important. A mean score can be calculated in each of the teaching behavior competence, scores ranging from 1.0-2.73 can be categorized as low clinical teaching effectiveness, a score of 2.74-5.34 can be categorized as moderate clinical teaching effectiveness and score ranging from 5.35-7.0 can be categorized as high clinical teaching effectiveness. This can be interpreted on how the respondents effectively deal on clinical instruction to the students, being a good role model, organized with high self-esteem and demonstrated good sense of humor. It also undergone a pilot testing among 45 respondents with the same norm group on the actual respondents. Based on the result of the pilot testing conducted in the five teaching behavior competencies, the reliability statistics for teaching ability (items 1-16), teaching competence (items 17-25) and evaluation (items 26-35) showed a value of 0.832, 0.713 and 0.786 respectively. Lastly, interpersonal relations (items 36-41) and personality (items 42-48) has a revealed a Cronbach's alpha of 0.660 and 0.807 respectively. The values presented in the five teaching behavior competencies were accepted.

Procedure

To facilitate the study, the researcher first asked permission from the Dean of the Graduate School to conduct the study. Afterward, the researcher also sent a letter to the CDU Human Resource Department for approval to have an official list of names of medical-related programs among faculty employed in the academic year 2017-2018. Lastly, the researcher sent a letter to the respective dean from each colleges for an approval to implement the study for approximately 10 to 15 minutes among the faculty involved. Schedule of implementation will be arranged according to the availability of the faculty member and the researcher. Several evaluations were taken to comply with the guidelines set by the research office such as title screening, determination of the sample size and pilot testing of the modified questionnaire. A set of 20 respondents from each different colleges which offers medical-related programs in Velez College were recruited for the pilot testing that serve as a trial run for the study and to assess the validity and reliability of the emotional intelligence scale and modified clinical teacher effectiveness inventory as part of the tool since some of the items were modified to tailor fit the type of respondents who will be involved in the study. The tool involves self-evaluation questionnaire which does not affect the validity and reliability of the result considering that the original tool was identified as self-evaluation questionnaire. An

approval letter was submitted to the respective deans of the said college. Afterwards, an ethical review of the paper was done by the Institutional Ethics Review Committee of the Cebu Doctors' University for ethical concerns. Lastly, thesis proposal paper was subjected to anti-plagiarism evaluation to ensure that the contents are properly written and correctly cited as required. The thesis proposal was then evaluated by a panel committee through a proposal hearing. Implementation of the study was conducted as per approval of the panel committee.

To get significant information for the study, the researcher along with the mentor had set a date for the schedule and orientation of the respondents prior to implementation. After, the respondents understand and agree to the terms of the study, an informed consent form were given to the respondents who complied. The respondents as per programs in the different colleges had answer the two (2) research instrument – Emotional Intelligence Scale and Modified Clinical Teacher Effectiveness Inventory. Instructions were discussed by the researcher; also the researcher in charge was available for any questions and clarifications regarding the study. Upon submission the researcher should ensure that all items were responded.

Lastly, the data was recorded and tabulated for statistical treatment and data analysis. Based on the findings an integration of proposals of CDU Development Plan among the faculty in the different medical-related programs were formulated to include in their respective colleges. Hence, the results of the study will be shredded eight (8) months after the implementation.

Ethical Considerations

Observing ethical standards in research is essential. At the core, this helped shape the true aims of the study, such as knowledge, truth, and avoidance of error and promoted values essential to collaborative work, such as trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness. To ensure ethical research, this study followed and respected the principles of research ethics from the Belmont Report (2010). These principles respect a person's autonomy, beneficence and non-maleficence, justice, informed consent, confidentiality and data protection, integrity, and conflict of interest.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Faculty of the Medical-Related Programs

The findings of the study are presented in tables.

Table 1 shows the first component of the emotional intelligence scale, the perception of emotions. emotional intelligence consists of perception of emotions, managing emotions in the self, social skills on managing others' emotions and utilizing emotions showed a mean score of 3.99, 4.19, 3.84 and 4.14 respectively which interpreted as high emotional intelligence. It indicates that the respondents has greater perception on recognizing emotions towards self and others, social skills in managing and utilizing emotions for developing quality attitudes that enhances in solving problem, clinical decision and a significant predictor of perceived successful leadership skills. It also signifies more positive personality traits, such as enthusiasm, confidence, competence and building mutual respect with each other.

Table 1. *Emotional Intelligence Mean Score*

<i>Components</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Perception of Emotions	3.99	.52	High
Managing Emotions in the Self	4.19	.48	High
Social Skills on Managing Others' Emotions	3.84	.60	High
Utilizing Emotions	4.14	.51	High

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution on the level of emotional intelligence in terms of perception of emotions, managing emotions in the self, social skills on managing others' emotions and utilizing emotions. Based on the data presented above, most of the respondents had high emotional intelligence in all the components which indicates greater ability to handle one's emotion and able recognize several non-verbal messages from other people to establish good communication and rapport among colleagues, students and others. These respondents were very optimistic, flexible to any changes and usually not bothered by any criticism that leads them to be remain focused on the outcomes, rather than feeling offended. The result of the study can be anchored by Goleman's theory of emotional intelligence that states when a person has high emotional intelligence, he/she tends to have an increase self-awareness, self-regulation, internal motivation, empathy and social skills. Therefore, the faculty members were academically competent, high sense of humor and able to balance personal and work-related aspects.

In line with this, the inherent characteristics of a Filipino faculty has an ability to overcome challenges despite of the personal crises, tragedy, trauma and could become more wiser, bolder and powerful. Another study by Dunn & Hansford, stated that a faculty with higher emotional intelligence was reposted as being more competent teachers. Building mutual respect with students and facilitating the development of student/staff rapport in the clinical setting are interpersonal skills that assist faculty to promote a positive learning environment. Students identified interpersonal skills such as clinical faculty's quality of answering questions and specificity of feedback as significantly associated with their learning (Makarem et al., 2001).

On the other hand, minority of the respondents showed low emotional intelligence on all the components. It implied that the respondents able to experience not being loved and cared by his/her family and peers which results not to rely on others for support and no sense

of belongingness in the workplace. Individuals with low emotional intelligence can still enhance and develop his/her emotional aspects by engaging an activity that would increase his/her self-esteem in establishing good communication to others. This can also help to lessen the occurrence of anxiety and stress in the workplace and were affected by negative events easily. As supported by Allen et al. (2012) states that some of the behavioral manifestations among people with low emotional intelligence includes being impatient and gets easily frustrated. Emotions are the on-off switch of learning process since having low emotional intelligence may hinder an individual's learning process but does not limit the knowledge to learn new things around him/her.

The overall result of emotional intelligence for the majority of medical-related faculty showed high perception on recognizing emotions towards self and others, social skills in managing and utilizing emotions for developing quality attitudes that enhances in solving problem, clinical decision and a significant predictor of perceived successful leadership skills (Stone et al., 2005). This indicates that the respondents had an adequate capacity to manage their emotional and social functioning with some areas of strength and areas that required improvement (Bar-On, 2006). A faculty who was reported with higher emotional intelligence signifies more positive personality traits, such as having a positive outlook on life (Bar-On, 2006). With these traits, the faculty would be more likely to demonstrate enthusiasm and confidence in the clinical setting and be nonjudgmental with the students. This is consistent with the literature, where nursing students have identified that faculty with positive personality traits such as a sense of humor and enthusiasm can promote their learning (Wolf, Bender, Beitz, Wieland, & Vito, 2004).

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Emotional Intelligence*

Components	High Emotional Intelligence		Low Emotional Intelligence	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Perception of Emotions	156	83.9	30	16.1
Managing Emotions in the Self	177	95.2	9	4.8
Social Skills on Managing Others' Emotions	144	77.4	42	22.6
Utilizing Emotions	176	94.6	10	5.4

Table 3 shows the clinical teaching effectiveness composed of teaching ability, teaching competence, evaluation, interpersonal relations and personality showed a mean score of 5.84, 5.91, 5.61, 6.05 and 5.98 respectively that denotes high clinical teaching effectiveness. Most of the respondents has high teaching behavior in transmitting theoretical and clinical knowledge used in the practice and the attitudes toward the profession, greater occurrence in the type and amount of feedback regarding his/her clinical performance, clearer state of common interest or communication between two or more people and higher totality on attitudes, emotional tendencies, and character traits in the clinical setting.

Table 3. *Clinical Teaching Effectiveness Mean Score*

Component	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Teaching Ability	5.84	.69	High
Teaching Competence	5.91	.74	High
Evaluation	5.61	.72	High
Interpersonal Relations	6.05	.74	High
Personality	5.98	.74	High

Table 4 shows the frequency and percentage distribution on the level of clinical teaching effectiveness in terms of teaching ability, teaching competence, evaluation, interpersonal relations and personality. Based on the data presented above, most of the respondents had high clinical teaching effectiveness in all the components which indicates proficient teaching behavior as a clinical instructor in transmitting theoretical and clinical knowledge to facilitate instruction for students could further understand and accepts the variations in patient care, increased involvement in dealing clinical decision in the health care settings. These respondents has a strong personal and social interaction in establishing a mutual respect to one another, high self-esteem, showed interests in the welfare of the students through listening their concern attentively and highly accentuate the importance of empathy.

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Clinical Teaching Effectiveness*

Components	High Clinical Teaching Effectiveness		Moderate Clinical Teaching Effectiveness	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Teaching Ability	137	73.7	49	26.3
Teaching Competence	142	76.3	44	23.7
Evaluation	119	64.0	67	36.0
Interpersonal Relations	149	80.1	37	19.9
Personality	148	79.6	38	20.4

On the other hand, minority of the respondents showed moderate clinical teaching effectiveness on all the components. It implied that the respondents can manage his/her teaching behavior in handling various issues related to student-teacher relationship but has difficulty in perceiving the level of understanding to others or vice-versa. It may limit the respondents to establish rapport with others due to irrelevant situation that takes place such as difficult to adapt changes, peer pressure and lack of enthusiasm.

Generally, the result of clinical teaching effectiveness for the majority of medical-related faculty showed high teaching behavior in

transmitting theoretical and clinical knowledge used in the practice and the attitudes toward the profession, greater occurrence in the type and amount of feedback regarding his/her clinical performance, clearer state of common interest or communication between two or more people and higher totality on attitudes, emotional tendencies, and character traits in the clinical setting.

Table 5 shows the relationship between the components of the emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness. Perception of emotions in relation to teaching ability, evaluation, interpersonal relations and personality showed a $r_s = .320, .323, .301$ and $.314$ respectively which indicates low positive value. This implies a weak positive correlation in terms of understanding the non-verbal messages of other people through observing their facial expressions and listening the tone of their voice to the teaching behavior of a clinical instructor such as transmitting knowledge, skills, and attitude that creates conducive learning environment, type and amount of feedback regarding his/her clinical performance in the clinical setting, state of common interest or communication between two or more people and totality of the respondent's attitudes, emotional tendencies, and character traits, which are not specifically related to teaching. Perception of emotions in relation to teaching competence showed a $r_s = .233$ which indicates negligible value. This implies no correlation between understanding the non-verbal messages of other people through observing their facial expressions and listening the tone of their voice to the teaching competence of a faculty's theoretical and clinical knowledge used in the practice and the attitudes toward the profession.

Table 5. Spearman's Rho Correlation Between Emotional Intelligence and Clinical Teaching Effectiveness

Components	Spearman rho Coefficient	Interpretation
Perception of Emotions & Teaching Ability	.320	Low positive
Perception of Emotions & Teaching Competence	.233	Negligible
Perception of Emotions & Evaluation	.323	Low positive
Perception of Emotions & Interpersonal Relations	.301	Low positive
Perception of Emotions & Personality	.314	Low positive
Managing Emotions in the Self & Teaching Ability	.370	Low positive
Managing Emotions in the Self & Teaching Competence	.241	Negligible
Managing Emotions in the Self & Evaluation	.404	Low positive
Managing Emotions in the Self & Interpersonal Relations	.358	Low positive
Managing Emotions in the Self & Personality	.317	Low positive
Social Skills on Managing Others' Emotions & Teaching Ability	.296	Negligible
Social Skills on Managing Others' Emotions & Teaching Competence	.244	Negligible
Social Skills on Managing Others' Emotions & Evaluation	.364	Low positive
Social Skills on Managing Others' Emotions & Interpersonal Relations	.329	Low positive
Social Skills on Managing Others' Emotions & Personality	.351	Low positive
Utilizing Emotions & Teaching Ability	.297	Negligible
Utilizing Emotions & Teaching Competence	.273	Negligible
Utilizing Emotions & Evaluation	.371	Low positive
Utilizing Emotions & Interpersonal Relations	.270	Negligible
Utilizing Emotions & Personality	.326	Low positive

The second component was managing emotions in the self in relation to teaching ability, evaluation, interpersonal relations and personality showed a $r_s = .370, .404, .358$ and $.317$ respectively which revealed a low positive value. This implies a weak positive correlation specifically in the self-awareness and self-expression abilities of a faculty to the teaching behavior in terms of transmitting knowledge, skills, and attitude that creates conducive learning environment, type and amount of feedback regarding his/her clinical performance in the clinical setting, state of common interest or communication between two or more people and totality of the respondent's attitudes, emotional tendencies, and character traits, which are not specifically related to teaching. Managing of emotions in the self in relation to teaching competence showed a $r_s = .241$ which indicates negligible value. This implies no correlation between self-awareness and self-expression abilities to the teaching competence of a faculty in regards with theoretical and clinical knowledge used in the practice and the attitudes toward the profession.

Social skills on managing others' emotions in relation to the teaching evaluation, interpersonal relations and personality showed a $r_s = .364, .329,$ and $.351$ respectively which denotes low positive value. This implies a weak positive correlation on the social awareness, awareness of others' feelings or cooperative relationship building toward others to the teaching behavior of a faculty in the clinical setting through identifying the type and amount of feedback did the faculty enjoyed his/her profession, state of common interest or communication between two or more people and totality of the faculty's attitudes, emotional tendencies, and character traits, which are not specifically related to teaching. In relation to social skills on managing others' emotions to the teaching ability and teaching competence showed a $r_s = .296$ and $.244$ respectively indicates a negligible value which implies no correlation between social awareness and awareness of others' feelings to the teaching behavior of faculty in regards of transmitting theoretical and clinical knowledge used in the practice and the attitudes toward the profession.

The fourth component was the utilizing emotions in relation to teaching evaluation and personality showed a $r_s = .371$ and $.326$ respectively which signifies low positive value. This implies a weak correlation between the capacity of a faculty to regulate his/her emotions; situational coping, flexibility and problem solving essential for managing change to the teaching behavior in terms of identifying the type and amount of feedback did the faculty enjoyed his/her profession and totality of the faculty's attitudes, emotional

tendencies, and character traits, which involved his/her overall behavior. Moreover, utilizing emotions in relation to teaching ability, teaching competence and interpersonal relations showed a $r_s = .297, .273$ and $.270$ respectively revealed a negligible value. This implies that capacity of a faculty to regulate his/her emotions; situational coping, flexibility and problem solving essential for managing change has nothing to do with the teaching behavior of a faculty in such way of transmitting theoretical and clinical knowledge used in the practice and the attitudes toward the profession and clearer state of common interest or communication between two or more people in dealing with clinical decision-making.

Therefore, emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness showed low positive relationship. This means that level of one's own thinking, regulation and utilization of emotion in the self and others in solving problems and decision-making has low positive relation on the teaching behavior of a faculty on effectively prepare the students to "practice with patients, including individuals, families, groups, communities, and populations across the lifespan and across the continuum of health care environments. Low positive relationship between emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness can take place considering that there are teachers who can perform the job well in spite of a low level of emotional intelligence. It cannot be possible that there would be no relationship between these two factors, but positive relationship may take place in varying levels of relationship depending on individual cases.

Table 6 shows the proposed institutional faculty development plan that was integrated as to improve the college faculty scheme of Cebu Doctors' University. This can also be a guide in formulating activities intended for regulation of emotions, interpersonal growth and teaching behavior of a respondents in the clinical setting.

Proposal Title: "Sustaining and Enhancing Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Effectiveness Among Medical-Related Faculty"

Proposal Description: This plan includes a seminar, activities and workshop that will enrich the qualities of a faculty toward the work done by a trainers' who guide the process of personal change or professional development, basic skills in decision making, problem-solving techniques, and methods related to strategic thinking, etc. It also improve the understanding of one's own needs, emotions, abilities, and behavior, indicating that a person able to identify his or her own strengths and weaknesses to be more effective.

Rationale: This plan was intended to sustain the high emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness of the majority of the faculty and to develop those faculty who have low emotional intelligence and moderate clinical teaching effectiveness as to enhance their personal, emotional and social aspects in translating to know thyself and others' need. It aimed to integrate this proposal into the human behavior component of the faculty development plan to attain competent, exemplary performance of the entire medical-related faculty of Cebu Doctors' University.

Table 6. *Proposed Institutional Faculty Development Plan*

<i>Data Base</i>	<i>Proposals</i>
The findings showed that 30 out of 186 (16.1%) of the faculty had low result in the aspect of perception of emotions with a mean value of 3.99.	Activity: Lay It On the line Self-regard is the ability to respect and accept oneself as you are. Place an X on the chart to indicate on each line where you rate yourself. In which areas are you satisfied or dissatisfied? What could you do to improve the areas that need improvement? Balance is the key.
The findings showed that 9 out of 186 (4.8%) of the faculty had low result in the aspect of managing of emotions in the self with a mean value of 4.19.	Activity: Teen Spotlight Self-actualization is the ability to set goals and feel that you are accomplishing those goals. Using the newspaper layout, design a newspaper highlighting YOURSELF. Include your greatest accomplishment, a self-portrait of you doing something that you enjoy, headlines, etc. In the box at the top, give your newspaper a unique name.
The findings showed that 42 out of 186 (22.6%) of the faculty had low result in the aspect of social skills on managing others' emotions with a mean value of 3.84.	Activity: High Five (Group Work) Building self-esteem in yourself and others is an easy task when giving and receiving compliments. You will need a large sheet of colored construction paper taped to the back of each person and a colored marker or crayon. Each person will move around the room and write at least one positive comment on every other person's paper. Comments should draw attention to that person's strengths. When finished, ask each person to remove the paper and read what others have said about him or her.
The findings showed that 10 out of 186 (5.4%) of the faculty had low result in the aspect of utilizing emotions with a mean value of 4.14.	Activity: Today I Feel... Use the picture to identify how you feel today. Once you determine your emotional feelings, you can respond by making smart choices as you interact with others throughout the day. Recognizing your feelings and making a conscious decision to react positively to your feelings is the difference between a good day and a bad day. You have the capability to make this the best day of your life.
The findings showed that 49 out of 186 (26.3%) of the faculty had moderate result in the aspect of teaching ability with a mean value of 5.84.	Workshop: Comprehensive faculty development program Professional Development as to widen his/her ideas on what specific role to act on. Instructional Development access to teaching-improvement activity, peer coaching and mentoring.
The findings showed that 44 out of 186 (23.7%) of the faculty had moderate result in the aspect of teaching competence with a mean value of 5.91.	Workshop: Comprehensive faculty development program Leadership Development used to develop the skills of scholarship to effectively evaluate and advance medical education.

The findings showed that 67 out of 186 (36.0%) of the faculty had moderate result in the aspect of evaluation with a mean value of 5.61.	Organizational Development empowering the faculty to excel in their roles by abiding the rules and regulation.
The findings showed that 37 out of 186 (19.9%) of the faculty had moderate result in the aspect of interpersonal relations with a mean value of 6.05.	Seminar: Job Enrichment Activity Sharing of good practices, professional readings and ideas within, enhancement of professionalism and ultimate improvement of students' learning outcomes. Engaging in, facilitating or promoting collegial sharing, collaborative teaching peer class observation among colleagues for the betterment of teaching and student learning. Production and (first) delivery of a professional presentation on good/informed practices for sharing among teachers during school staff development days organized on a district basis. Visit to other schools or institutions to have professional exchange and sharing of experience about successful innovation; good practices in teaching.
The findings showed that 38 out of 186 (20.4%) of the faculty had moderate result in the aspect of personality with a mean value of 5.98.	Activity: The Box of Fears An individual or group work that includes a card stipulated with "I'm afraid of..." place inside the box and sit on the floor forming a circle. At a time each individual takes a card from the box and reads the sentence a loud. Then the facilitator will record his/her fears on the board. After the session, discuss the opinions and try to find a solution. Activity: Guess the Word Simply guessing with character adjectives and define one of the words or give examples until the partner able to guess. You could also limit them to giving examples of actions that illustrate particular personality words. They could also make statements about who the word that they are describing with.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the statement of conclusion was made that focused on emotional intelligence and clinical teaching effectiveness showed low positive relationship among the faculty of medical-related faculty of Cebu Doctors' University. This means that level of one's own thinking, regulation and utilization of emotion in the self and others in solving problems and decision-making has low positive relation on the teaching behavior of a faculty on effectively prepare the students to "practice with patients, including individuals, families, groups, communities, and populations across the lifespan and across the continuum of health care environments. With the proposal entitled "Enhancing Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Effectiveness Among Medical-Related Faculty" that was integrated to the institutional faculty development plan as to improve the faculty with low emotional intelligence and moderate clinical teaching effectiveness in regards with personal, emotional and social aspects in translating to know thyself and others' need. It aimed to attain a competent, exemplary performance of the entire medical-related faculty of Cebu Doctors' University. This plan includes an activities and workshop that can enhance the competency of a faculty in terms of personal, emotional and social interactions in collaboration with the administration in fulfilling the goal to achieve a recognized programs in the different health allied institution.

References

- Adair, C., & McConnell, F.A. (2014). Reclaiming the roots of practice through emotional intelligence. *New Mexico Nurse*, 59 (3), 6-7.
- Allen, D. E., Ploeg, J., & Kaasalainen, S. (2012). The relationship between emotional intelligence and CTE of nursing faculty. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 28 (4), 231240.
- Allison-Jones, L. (2002). Student and faculty perceptions of teaching effectiveness of full-time and part-time associate degree nursing faculty (Order No. 3061240). Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global (305489901). <http://ezproxy.gc.cuny.edu/login?url=http://search.proquest.com/docview/305489901?accountid=7287>
- Allison-Jones, L., & Hirt, J. (2004). Comparing the clinical teaching effectiveness of part-time and full-time faculty. *Nursing Education Perspectives*, 25 (5), 238-245.
- American Association of Colleges of Nursing (AACN). (2008). The essentials of baccalaureate education for professional nursing practice. Retrieved 10/7/2016 from <https://search.yahoo.com/yhs/search?p=aacn+2008&ei=UTF-8&hspart=mozilla&hsimp=yhs-001>
- Assanova, M., & McGuire, M. (2009). Applicability analysis of Emotional Intelligence theory (Master's thesis). Indiana University. Retrieved from http://indiana.edu/~spea/pubs/undergrad-honors/honors_vol.3_no.1.pdf
- Bansal, G., Tyczkowski, B., Vandenbouten, C., Reilly, J., Kubsch, S., & Jakkola, R. (2015). Emotional Intelligence and Nursing Leadership Styles Among Nurse Managers. *Wolters Kluwer Health Inc.*, Vol. 39, No. 2, pp. 172-180.
- Bar-On, R. (2006). The Bar-On model of emotional-social intelligence (ESI). *Psicothema*, 18, 13-25.
- Benner, P., Sutphen, M., Leonard, V., & Day, L. (2010). *Educating nurses: A call for radical transformation*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Brackett, M. A., Palomera, R., Mojsa-Kaja, J., Reyes, M. R., & Salovey, P. (2010). Emotionregulation ability, burnout, and job

satisfaction among British secondary-school teachers. *Psychology in the Schools*, 47 (4), 406-417.

Chan, D. W. (2004). Perceived emotional intelligence and self-efficacy among Chinese secondary school teachers in Hong Kong. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 36 (8), 1781-1795.

Chan, J., Sit, E., & Lau, W. M. (2014). Conflict management styles, emotional intelligence and implicit theories of personality of nursing students. *Nurse Education Today*, 34 (6), 934-939.

Ciarrochi, J., Chan, A. Y. C., & Bajgar, J. (2001). Measuring emotional intelligence in adolescents. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 31, 1105-1119.

Downey, L., Papageorgiou, V., & Stough, C. (2005). Examining the relationship between leadership, emotional intelligence and intuition in senior female managers. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 27, 250-264.

Dunn, S., & Hansford, B. (1997). Undergraduate nursing students' perceptions of their clinical learning environment. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 25, 1299-1306.

Fluit, C. R. M. G., Bolhuis, S., Grol, R., Laan, R., & Wensing, M. (2010). Assessing the quality of clinical teachers: A systematic review of content and quality of questionnaires for assessing clinical teachers. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 25(12), 1337-1345. doi:10.1007/s11606-010-1458-y

Freshwater, D., & Stickley, T. (2004). The heart of the art: Emotional intelligence in nurse education. *Nursing Inquiry*, 11, 91-98.

Freudenthaler, H. H., Neubauer, A. C., & Haller, U. (2008). Emotional intelligence: Instruction effects and sex differences in emotional management abilities. *Journal of Individual Differences*, 29, 105-115.

Gaberson, K. & Oermann, M. (2010). *Clinical Teaching Strategies in Nursing*. New York, NY: Springer Publishing Company.

Gardner, H. (1995). *Reflections on Multiple Intelligences: Myths and Messages*. Phi Delta Kappan, 77, 200-209.

Gillespie M. (2002) Student – teacher connection in clinical nursing education. *Journal of Advanced Nursing* 37, 566–576.

Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: Why it matters more than IQ*. New York, NY: Bantam.

Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with Emotional Intelligence*. New York. Bantam Books.

Görgens-Ekermans, G., & Brand, T. (2012). Emotional intelligence as a moderator in the stress burnout relationship: A questionnaire study on nurses. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 21, 2275-2285.

Hampton, D. (2015). What's The Difference Between Feelings And Emotions? <https://www.thebestbrainpossible.com/whats-the-difference-between-feelings-and-emotions/>

Hanson, K., & Stenvig, T. (2008). The good clinical nursing educator and the baccalaureate nursing clinical experience: Attributes and praxis. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 47 (1), 38-42.

Jaeger, A. J. (2003). Job competencies and the curriculum: An inquiry into emotional intelligence in graduate professional education. *Research in Higher Education*, 44(6), 615-639

James, W. (1884). What is an Emotion? *Mind*, 9, 188-205.

Karimi, L., Leggat, S. G., Donohue, L., & Cooper, G. E. (2014). Emotional rescue: The role of emotional intelligence and emotional labour on well-being and job-stress among community nurses. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 70 (1), 176-186. doi:10.1111/jan.12185

Knox, J. E., & Mogan, J. (1985). Important clinical teacher behaviours as perceived by university nursing faculty, students and graduates. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 10, 25-30.

Kotzabassaki, S., Panou, M., Dimou, F., Karabagli, A., Koutsopoulou, B., & Ikonomou, U. (1997). Nursing students' and faculty's perceptions of the characteristics of 'best' and 'worst' clinical teachers: A replication study. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 26, 817-818.

Lee, W., Cholowski, K., & Williams, A. (2002). Nursing students' and clinical educators' perceptions of characteristics of effective clinical educators in an Australian university school of nursing. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 39, 412-420.

Lisko, S. A., & O' Dell, V. (2010). Integration of theory and practice: Experiential learning and nursing education. *Nursing Education Perspectives*, 31(2), 106-108.

Lovric, R., Prilc, N., Barc, I., Pluzaric, J., Puseljic, S., Berecki, I., & Radic, R. (2014). Specificities and differences in nursing students' perceptions of nursing clinical faculties' competencies. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 30 (5), 406-417.

Makarem, S., Dumit, N., Adra, M., & Kassak, K. (2001). Teaching effectiveness and learning outcomes of baccalaureate nursing

- students in a critical care practicum: A Lebanese experience. *Nursing Outlook*, 49, 43–49.
- Malik, S. & Shadid, S. (2016). Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Academic Performance among Business Students in Pakistan. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, Vol. 38, No. 1, pp. 197-208.
- Mavroveli, S., Petrides, K. V., Rieffe, C., & Bakker, F. (2007). Trait emotional intelligence, psychological well-being and peer-rated social competence in adolescence. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 25, 263 – 275
- Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional intelligence? In P. Salovey & D. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional development and emotional intelligence: Educational implications* (pp. 3-31). New York, NY: Basic.
- Mogan, J., & Knox, J. (1983). Students' perceptions of clinical teaching. *Nursing Papers*, 15, 4-13.
- Mogan, J., & Knox, J. E. (1987). Characteristics of "best" and "worst" clinical teachers as perceived by university nursing faculty and students. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 12, 331-337.
- Mosca, Caroline K., "The Relationship Between Clinical Teaching Effectiveness and Emotional Intelligence in Clinical Nurse Faculty in Pre-licensure Baccalaureate Programs in New York State" (2017). CUNY Academic Works. Retrieved from https://academicworks.cuny.edu/gc_etds/1846.
- Myers, D. G. (2004). *Theories of Emotion*. Psychology: Ninth Edition. New York, NY: Worth Publishers.
- Nwadinigwe, I. & Azuka-Obieke, U. (2012). The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Lagos, Nigeria. *Scholarlink Research Institute Journals*, pp 395-401.
- Ondrejka, D. (2013). *Affective teaching in nursing: Connecting to feelings, values, and inner awareness*. New York, NY: Springer.
- Payne, W. L. (1985). A study of emotion: Developing emotional intelligence; self-integration; relating to fear, pain, and desire. *Dissertation Abstracts International, Section A. Humanities and Social Sciences*.
- Petrides, K. V. (2010). Trait emotional intelligence theory. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 3, 136-139.
- Petrides, K. V., & Furnham, A. (2001). Trait emotional intelligence: Psychometric investigation with reference to established trait taxonomies. *European Journal of Personality*, 15, 425-448.
- Roja, M. Panimalar, N. Sasikumar, and M. Parimala Fathima. "A Study on Emotional Maturity and Self Concept at Higher Secondary Level." *Research in Psychology and Behavioral Sciences* 1.5 (2013): 81-83
- Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition, and Personality*, 9, 185-211.
- Schutte, N. S., & Loi, N. M. (2014). Connections between emotional intelligence and workplace flourishing. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 66, 134-139. doi:10.1016/j.paid.2014.03.031
- Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., & Bhullar, N. (2009). The Assessing Emotions Scale. In C. Stough, D. Saklofske, & J. Parker (Eds.), *The assessment of emotional intelligence* (pp. 119-135). New York, NY: Springer.
- Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., Hall, L. E., Haggerty, D. J., Cooper, J. T., Golden, C. J., & Dornheim, L. (1998). Development and validation of a measure of emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 25, 167-177.
- Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., & Thorsteinsson, E. B. (2013). Increasing emotional intelligence through training: Current status and future directions. *International Journal of Emotional Education*, 15 (1), 56-72.
- Singh, I., & Jha, A. (2012). Teacher effectiveness in relation to emotional intelligence among medical and engineering faculty members. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 8 (4), 667. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.5964/ejop.v8i4.483>
- Stone, H., Parker, J. D., & Wood, L. M. (2005). Report on the Ontario Principals' Council Leadership Study. <http://www.eiconsortium.org/>
- Thorndike, E. (1920). Intelligence and its uses. *Harper's Magazine*, 140, 227–235.
- Thorndike, R. L., & Stein, S. (1937). An evaluation of the attempts to measure social intelligence. *The Psychological Bulletin*, 34 (5), 275-285.
- Tigelaar, D., Dolmans, D., Wolfhagen, I., & Van Der Vleuten, C. (2004). Teaching competencies in higher education. *Higher Education*, 48, 253-268.
- Wetherbee, E., Nordrum, J. T., & Giles, S. (2008). Effective teaching behaviors of APTAcredentialed versus noncredentialed clinical instructors. *Journal of Physical Therapy Education*, 22 (1), 65-74.
- Wolf, A., Bender, P., Beitz, J., Wieland, D., and Vito, K. (2004) Strengths and Weaknesses of Faculty Teaching Performance Reported

by Undergraduate and Graduate Nursing Students. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 20, 118-128.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.profnurs.2004.03.003>

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